

Investigations on the Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction between Potassium Peroxydisulphate and Malic Acid

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The reaction between potassium peroxydisulphate and malic acid has been studied from the view point of kinetics. It progresses by a first order path at 50° and 55°. Increase of temperature results in the variation of order, when it is found to progress bimolecularly in the beginning and unimolecularly till completion. Temperature coefficient and activation energy of the reaction are found to be 2.7 and 22.11 kcal respectively. H⁺ ion exerts a catalysing influence on the reaction rate. These observations have been explained by a chain mechanism leading to a kinetic expression for the reaction rate.

The peroxydisulphate ion is a strong oxidant in aqueous solution and reactions involving this ion are generally slow at room temperature. The reaction between $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and several reducing ions such as oxalate, formate, tartrate etc., have been studied kinetically and various mechanisms have been advanced to explain the reaction in each case. The work prior to 1961 has been comprehensively reviewed by D. A. House¹. Saxena and Singhal² studied the reduction of peroxydisulphate by tartaric acid in connection with the induced reactions. They found its order to vary from 2 to 1 with the progress of the reaction and suggested a mechanism leading to a kinetic expression for the reaction rate. The recent review by Waters³ on the oxidation processes in general and of some α -hydroxy acids by Mn (III)⁴⁻⁶, Ce (IV)⁷⁻¹⁰ and vanadium¹¹ ions throws much light on the mechanisms of oxidation and its dependence on the nature of the oxidant.

A search of literature reveals that the kinetics of reduction of peroxydisulphate by malic acid remains hitherto unstudied. The reaction appeared interesting, particularly because of the presence of one hydroxyl group in the acid molecule. The present communication deals with our investigations on the kinetics of the reduction of peroxydisulphate by malic acid with a view to arrive at a probable mechanism of the reaction.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of $K_2S_2O_8$ and malic acid (both Analar quality, B.D.H. and Sterling samples) were prepared in double distilled water. Solution of $K_2S_2O_8$ was prepared just before start of the reaction. Required amounts of freshly prepared solution contained in Pyrex conical flasks were placed in a thermostat to attain the desired temperature. The reaction was started by mixing the reactants at desired concentrations. After suitable intervals of time 10 ml. aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and residual peroxydisulphate estimated by the usual method¹². The unimolecular and bimolecular rate constants were calculated by the usual formulae.

The reaction was studied at 50°, 55°, 60°, 65° and 70° with a view to find out the order, temperature coefficient and activation energy of the reaction. Preliminary experiments showed that 0.02M concentration of each reactant and 60° temperature was suitable for investigations.

TABLE I

t	(a) Temp. 70°		(b) Temp. 65°		(c)° Temp. 60°		(d)Temp. 55°		(e) Temp. 50°	
	$K_1 \times 10^3$	$K_2 \times 10^3$								
0 min.	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
15 "	10.27	1.134	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
30 "	9.819	1.165	6.761	0.7654	3.517	0.3703	2.104	0.218	1.014	0.103
45 "	8.786	1.100	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
60 "	8.455	1.124	6.092	0.7504	3.718	0.4167	2.176	0.2373	1.032	0.106
75 "	8.196	1.55	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
90 "	8.166	1.230	6.023	0.8156	3.498	0.4111	2.235	0.2551	1.049	0.109
105 "	8.071	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
120 "	7.894	1.343	5.950	0.8856	3.336	0.4104	2.228	0.3129	1.065	0.113
135 "	7.849	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
150 "	7.894	1.542	5.811	0.9458	3.188	0.4086	2.244	0.2720	1.084	0.118
165 "	7.812	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
180 "	7.816	1.748	5.564	0.9763	3.027	0.4023	2.197	0.2790	1.035	0.1138
195 "	7.902	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
210 "	8.071	2.160	5.640	1.102	2.935	0.4057	2.181	0.2821	1.063	0.1190
240 "	8.112	2.552	5.694	1.242	2.889	0.4167	1.113	0.2821	1.089	0.1245
270 "	—	—	—	—	2.938	0.3680	2.072	0.2834	1.065	0.1230
300 "	—	—	5.640	1.512	2.893	0.4604	2.049	0.2888	1.050	0.1256
330 "	—	—	—	—	2.932	0.4944	2.039	0.2968	1.038	0.1238
360 "	—	—	—	—	2.917	0.5138	2.041	0.3076	1.072	0.1307
390 "	—	—	—	—	2.843	0.5206	1.995	0.3082	1.064	0.1321
420 "	—	—	—	—	2.868	0.5534	2.018	0.3240	1.063	0.1339
450 "	—	—	—	—	2.829	0.5719	1.991	0.3288	1.098	0.1421
480 "	—	—	—	—	2.810	0.5929	2.030	0.3505	1.099	0.1447
510 "	—	—	—	—	2.882	0.6564	—	—	1.069	0.1417
540 "	—	—	—	—	2.891	0.6966	—	—	1.074	0.1455
600 "	—	—	—	—	2.953	0.8137	—	—	1.027	0.1417

From the values of k_1 and k_2 it is observed that at 50° and 55°, the reaction follows first order while at higher temperatures there is an initial period of second order path followed by the first order till completion of the reaction. The temperature coefficient of the reaction as calculated from the mean unimolecular values comes out to be 2.73 between 50°/60°; 2.71 between 55°/65° and 2.70 between 60°/70°. The corresponding values for the activation energy are 21.61, 22.11 and 22.7 kcal.

Fig. 1 represents the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ which is a straight line. The energy of activation as given from the slope of this line, in the temperature range studied, came out to be 22.11 kcal.

FIG. 1

Order of the reaction.

Besides the integration method, other methods were also employed to determine the order of this reaction.

TABLE II

Malic acid = 0.02 M, $K_2S_2O_8$ = 0.02 M

Temperature °C	50°	55°	60°	65°	70°
$K_1 \times 10^3$ (Slope method)	0.9212	2.0727	2.9939	5.5962	7.830
$K_1 \times 10^3$ (Integration method)	1.068	2.109	3.196	5.827	7.965

FIG. 2

Fig. 2 shows $\log a/a-x$ vs T plots for different temperatures, which are straight lines passing through the origin, as required for the first order reactions. The unimolecular rate constants calculated from the slope of the lines are given in table II.

The velocity of reaction between peroxydisulphate and malic acid may be represented by the equation:

$$-\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} = kC_1^m C_2^n$$

Where C_1 and C_2 are the concentrations of peroxydisulphate and malic acid respectively and $(m+n)$ represents the total order of the reaction. For determining m and n , two sets of experiments were performed in which the concentrations of malic acid (C'_2 and C''_2) were varied but kept in large excess to that of peroxydisulphate. The concentration of peroxydisulphate was kept constant in both cases. The unimolecular velocity constant (k'_1 and k''_1) were calculated for both the experiments, which gave the value of 'm'. The results are summarised in table III.

TABLE III

Temperature 60°

t	(K ₂ S ₂ O ₈) ₀ =0.005 M (C ₁) (Malic acid) ₀ =0.05 M (C' ₂)			(K ₂ S ₂ O ₈) ₀ =0.005 M (C ₁) (Malic acid) ₀ =0.10 M (C'' ₂)			
	(a-x)		K' ₁	(a-x)		K'' ₁	
0	min	9.9	ml	—	9.9	ml	—
30	„	8.7	„	0.004370	9.0	„	0.003178
60	„	7.7	„	0.004180	8.9	„	0.002936
90	„	6.8	„	0.004175	7.8	„	0.002649
120	„	6.1	„	0.004035	7.3	„	0.002539
180	„	4.7	„	0.004234	6.6	„	0.002530
240	„	3.4	„	0.004453	5.8	„	0.002228
300	„	2.6	„	0.004457	4.7	„	0.002484

The value of n was calculated by the expression:

$$n = \frac{\log k'_1/k''_1}{\log C'_2/C''_2}$$

Its value comes out to be 0.07, thus the total order of the reaction by this method is 1.07.

Half life method:

In the case of first order reactions the half life is given by the expression

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\ln 2}{k}$$

and it is independent of the initial concentration. This has been verified graphically for the reaction under study, where it was found that the time intervals for the amount of peroxy-

disulphate to decrease to half its value were all equal. The rate constants as calculated from such graphs at different temperatures and reactant concentrations are given in table IV a.

TABLE IV (a)

Concentration			Temperature	Half life		$K_1 \times 10^3$
0.02	M	each reactant	70°	87	mins.	7.96
	"		65°	120	"	5.77
	"		60°	240	"	2.99
	"		55°	342	"	2.02
0.04	M	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ & Malic acid }	60°	330	"	2.10
0.02	M					
0.02	M	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ & Malic acid }	60°	258	"	3.58
0.01	M					

TABLE IV (b)

Malic acid = K₂S₂O₈ = 0.02 M

Temperature	70	60	65
Rate $\frac{t_{\frac{3}{4}} - t_{\frac{1}{2}}}{t_{\frac{1}{2}}}$	1.0	1.0	1.0

The above table gives values at different temperatures for rate $(\frac{t_{3/4} - t_{1/2}}{t_{1/2}})$ which indicate first order reaction rate.¹³

TABLE V

Effect of concentration of the reactants on the reaction rate.

(A) $(\text{Malic acid})_0 =$	0.02M	Temp. 60°		
(K ₂ S ₂ O ₈) ₀ (M)	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.04
K ₁ × 10 ³	7.933	5.382	2.902	2.149
(B) $(\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_0 = 0.02M$	Temp. 60°			
(Malic acid) ₀ (M)	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.04
K ₁ × 10 ³	2.450	2.694	2.902	3.581

From the foregoing table it is observed that on increasing the concentration of peroxydisulphate the values for the unimolecular coefficients decrease. On increasing the concentration of malic acid, however, the values of k₁ increase linearly.

TABLE VI

Comparative study of the effect of Sulphuric Acid, Nitric Acid, Potassium Sulphate, Sodium Acetate and Oxygen on the reaction rate.

$(\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_0 = (\text{Malic acid})_0 = 0.02 M$		Temp. 60°				
	Nil	Oxygen at const. press	0.05 N H ₂ SO ₄	0.1 N K ₂ SO ₄	0.05 N HNO ₃	0.05 N Sod. acetate.
K ₁ × 10 ³	2.902	5.068	3.734	3.038	3.769	2.861

From the above table it is observed that oxygen and (H⁺) accelerate the reaction, whereas sodium acetate suppresses it. In each case the reaction was found to follow the first order rate with one or two initial k₁ values being slightly higher. A few observations indicated a slight promoting role of the glass surface on the reaction rate. Mercuric chloride was reduced by malic acid-peroxydisulphate system.

DISCUSSION

The reaction between K₂S₂O₈ and malic acid may be represented by the following stoichiometric equation.

Various products are formed in the oxidation of malic acid depending upon the nature of the oxidant used with the Co (IV) and Mn (III) formic acid and CO₂ has been reported (loc. cit.). In the case of peroxydisulphate (which is less potent oxidant than potassium permanganate under comparable conditions), we have detected malonic acid as the oxidation product by spot tests carried out with the system (Feigl, Spot Test). Carbon-dioxide is also evolved.

In view of the foregoing conclusions the reduction of S₂O₈²⁻ by malate ion can be explained by a chain mechanism analogous to that suggested for the uncatalysed reaction between peroxydisulphate and tartrate²:-

The primary step is characteristic of all peroxydisulphate oxidations and sequences 2 and 3 have been postulated as the mechanism for the aqueous decomposition of peroxydisulphate².

*The reaction between the semioxidised malate ions and oxygen in step 5 may involve 3 steps: the secondary alcoholic group of the acid is first oxidised to keto group and later to malonic acid as shown below.

